

MOSMIN: Multiscale Observation Services for Mining-related deposits

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BIOGRAPHY

Moritz Kirsch, Sandra Lorenz and Richard Gloaguen work at the Helmholtz Institute Freiberg for Resource Technology (HIF) in Germany, driving forward the institute's mission to develop advanced methodologies for the economy so that mineral and metalliferous raw materials can be made available and used more efficiently and recycled in an environmentally friendly manner. Moritz holds a PhD from the Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México and leads a group focused on Innovative Applications in the Department of Exploration. His research interests lie at the intersection of geology and technology, leveraging the latest digital tools to characterise mineral assemblages and understand geological processes.

SUMMARY

Our society's reliance on raw materials from mining generates residues such as rock wastes and tailings. Managing these materials is crucial due to environmental and safety risks, necessitating stable containment and pollution prevention. Despite technological advances, Earth-observation (EO)-based techniques are underutilized for monitoring these deposits, and multi-sensor field data integration remains limited. MOSMIN, an EU Horizon research project (2024–2026) is developing comprehensive services for geotechnical and environmental monitoring and valorization of mining-related deposits. Our methodology integrates optical and radar satellite data with high-resolution data from unoccupied aerial vehicles and site sensors, enhanced through machine learning for multi-scale data fusion. Non-invasive geophysical techniques such as distributed fibre-optic sensing and ambient noise seismic provide subsurface information, crucial for identifying resource potential and assessing internal structure and deformation to link cause and effect. Preliminary results from our pilot sites in the EU, South America, and Africa demonstrate the effectiveness of these integrative tools.

Key words: tailings, mine waste, monitoring, earth observation, UAV.

INTRODUCTION

Raw materials form the basis of the global economy and are essential to achieving climate goals, enabling energy and digital transformations, and supporting sustainable

prosperity. The recovery of raw materials from primary mineral deposits, however, produces vast quantities of mine wastes. Over 100 billion tonnes per year are being generated globally in approximately 3500 active mining waste facilities worldwide (Tayebi-Khorami et al., 2019). These numbers are expected to rise as demand for mineral commodities increases and ore grades decline. Tailings storage facilities (TSF) and waste rock dumps (WRD) are among the most visible legacies of a mining operation. They contain hazardous substances and pose stability risks that, if not managed properly, can have major environmental, social, and economic impacts. The industry has started to adopt new digital technology for geotechnical and environmental monitoring of mine waste deposits but existing systems still have deficiencies (Clarkson et al., 2020), such as i) the use of labor-intensive manual devices that yield very localized, one- or two-dimensional data, ii) the absence of comprehensive data management and integrated data analysis protocols, iii) the lack of instrumentation to measure critical geotechnical parameters, and iv) limitations in the spatial and temporal coverage of data to help understand geotechnical behavior and evolution of waste deposits.

Within this context, we would like to introduce and present preliminary results of the Horizon Europe project "MOSMIN" (Multiscale Observation Services for Mining-related Deposits). MOSMIN is developing holistic, full-site services for the geotechnical and environmental monitoring as well as valorization of mining-related deposits based on a combination of EO and in situ geophysical data. MOSMIN aims to optimize the monitoring practices of mine waste deposits by (a) including satellite data to leverage large coverage, and long-term spatial data archives, (b) utilizing innovative volumetric geophysical imaging technologies that yield relevant, high-resolution 3D geotechnical parameters and help to establish a link between surface expression and subsurface processes, and c) developing automated, real-time and online solutions to improve cost, time, and resource efficiency. In addition, (d) we will aggregate and integrate data across different scales for an improved whole-of-structure understanding.

METHODS

MOSMIN exploits the benefits of an integrated, multi-scale approach (Fig. 1) to enhance the applicability of earth observation data in the mining industry. While we place primary focus on satellite data, the inclusion of data from UAV-based sensors as well as ground-based geophysical techniques provides validation and offsets the limitations by single technology use. Copernicus Sentinel-2 multispectral data with a 10–20 m ground sampling distance and a high revisit frequency of 5 days are at the core of MOSMIN's spectral services and will be used for the monitoring of mine-related deposits on a large scale. In order to extend the capabilities of Sentinel-2 regarding spectral and spatial resolution, hyperspectral data from EnMAP and PRISMA as well as commercial

multispectral satellite data (WorldView-3) will be incorporated into the MOSMIN services. We are using Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (InSAR) analysis to measure ground displacements, relying primarily on Sentinel-1 C-band data, but ESA's third-party mission such as SAOCOM Europe data products, which makes use of L-band, will also be considered. Corner reflectors will be tested in at least one mine site as a means to improve the accuracy and reliability of the deformation measurement.

On the UAV scale, we are deploying photogrammetry and LiDAR, providing high-resolution 3D models and topographic maps of our targets to support the acquisition, integration, and correction of other data products. UAV-based hyperspectral imaging will be used to analyse the material composition at a high spatial resolution and to train deep learning algorithms for resolution enhancement and change detection of surface properties at the mine sites.

As a means of ground-truthing and to be able to relate remotely sensed surface expression to processes in the subsurface, we employ a number of efficient and low-impact geophysical techniques, including electrical resistivity tomography (ERT), ambient noise tomography (ANT) and distributed acoustic sensing (DAS). ERT is an effective methodology to detect possible water infiltrations in the tailings dam due to its sensitivity to changes in humidity, temperature, and salinity. ANT is not yet an established technique in the mining industry. As a passive technique, it has logistical advantages and a very low environmental impact. ANT yields 3D shear-wave velocity information below the seismic array from which subsurface structures can be identified. DAS offers proactive geotechnical monitoring and sub-surface imaging at high temporal and spatial resolution. It uses a fibre cable as a key component to monitor e.g. tailings dams continuously during operation with little maintenance.

Four mining companies are part of the MOSMIN consortium. These companies will provide access to mine sites in Sweden, Romania, Chile, and Zambia that are at different stages of development and have active monitoring programs for their extractive waste and stockpiles. The pilot sites focus on copper as a commodity because of its crucial role in modern society (Valenta et al., 2019). Because copper is found primarily in sulphide ore, waste produced in the extraction and processing of copper has a high potential for acid mine drainage (AMD) and the release of potentially toxic elements (PTEs) into the ecosystem.

RESULTS

In MOSMIN, we aim to leverage the diverse skillset of our multidisciplinary team and utilize pre-existing methods, tools, and algorithms originally designed for various applications beyond the mining industry, adapting and integrating them specifically for monitoring and assessing mine waste. Open-source software will be

integral to the MOSMIN outcomes to facilitate maximum compatibility with existing tools, ensure wide use in industry and academia, and guarantee transparency and reproducibility of research results. Based on extensive literature review and interviews with industry partners and potential customers of the MOSMIN services, we have assembled a portfolio of products that we consider to be industrially relevant and fit-for-purpose.

The products we envisage for raw material valorisation include spectral-derived surface maps of geology and secondary prospectivity, delineation of geological domains in the subsurface based on ANT, and volume estimations, particularly for stockpiles (Fig. 2). For geotechnical monitoring, we will offer interferometric ground motion monitoring, spatial and temporal analysis of surface water and moisture, geotechnical characterization of tailing dams based on hyperspectral imaging, geophysical imaging of subsurface structures and 3D hydrogeological parameters as well as internal strain measurements. In terms of environmental monitoring, our services include vegetation health and water quality assessments, land cover change detection, and mapping of contamination and gully erosion.

While these first-order solutions have their merit and have shown to be effective for geological valorisation (e.g., Zhang et al., 2023), geotechnical (e.g., Cacciuttolo and Cano, 2023) and environmental monitoring (e.g., Shang et al., 2009) in mine waste environments, the integration of earth observation and ground-based methods will allow a more comprehensive insight into the interactions between surface phenomena and subsurface processes, but there is at present limited published work (Clarkson et al., 2020). Using data collected and compiled at our pilot sites, we will generate case studies to demonstrate and communicate the effectiveness of our approach, providing best-practice examples of how our solutions can be applied in real-world settings.

With satellite data acquisition, processing, and validation progressing at all sites, we are preparing for environmental fieldwork at our closed mine pilot site in Sweden. Additionally, we are in the process of deploying DAS, ANT, and ERT instrumentation, along with corner reflectors, at our pilot sites in Zambia and Chile. The preliminary findings from these activities will be presented.

CONCLUSIONS

Mitigating the risks associated with TSF and WRD demands a comprehensive and multi-disciplinary approach. The project MOSMIN has the ambition to provide integrated, multi-scale, and fit-for-purpose services to complement existing solutions for enhanced monitoring and risk-informed rather than consequence-based decision-making. By integrating remote sensing technologies and geophysical survey data, we can analyse processes at small and large scales and effectively link surface expressions to underlying

mechanisms in the subsurface. We hope that this holistic approach will help to ensure safer and more sustainable management of mine waste facilities.

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Figure 1. Multi-scale monitoring concept and technologies of the MOSMIN project.

Figure 2. Deposit types, application areas, and first-order products of the MOSMIN services.